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Gandbolchilarning o‘yin texnikasi bo‘yicha dastlabki tayyorgarligini oshirish

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Annotatsiya: Qo‘l to‘pi tez sur‘atda o‘tadigan jamoaviy sport turi bo‘lib, u jismoniy tayyorgarlik, texnik mahorat va taktik ongni uyg‘unlashtirishni talab qiladi. Samarali boshlang‘ich tayyorgarlik o‘yinlarda yaxshi o‘ynay oladigan o‘yinchilarni etishtirishda hal qiluvchi rol o‘ynaydi. Ushbu maqola gandbolchilarni asosiy o‘yin texnikasiga o‘rgatish, ularning malakali sportchi sifatida rivojlanishi uchun mustahkam poydevor qo‘yishning turli usullarini o‘rganadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Qo‘l to‘pi, O‘yin texnikasi, strategiya, innovatsiya, Taktik tushuncha

Совершенствование начальной подготовки гандболистов по технике игры

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Аннотация: Гандбол – это динамичный командный вид спорта, требующий сочетания физической подготовки, технических навыков и тактической осведомленности. Эффективная начальная подготовка играет решающую роль в развитии игроков, способных хорошо выступать в играх. В этой статье рассматриваются различные способы обучения гандболистов основным приемам игры, чтобы заложить прочную основу для их развития как квалифицированных спортсменов.

Ключевые слова: Гандбол, Техника игры, стратегия, инновации, Тактическая концепция

Improving the initial training of handball players in playing technique

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Abstract: Handball is a fast-paced team sport that requires a combination of physical fitness, technical skill and tactical awareness. Effective initial training plays a crucial role in developing players who can perform well in games. This article explores different ways to teach handball players basic game techniques to lay a solid foundation for their development as skilled athletes.

Key words: Handball, Game technique, strategy, innovation, Tactical concept

Kirish.

Qo'l to'pi – bu jismoniy kuch, tezlik va taktik ko'nikmalarni talab qiladigan sport turi. Yangi o'yinchilarni tayyorlashda dastlabki texnik tayyorgarlik muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqolada qo'l to'pichilarning o'yin texnikasini oshirish uchun qo'llaniladigan asosiy usullar va mashg'ulotlar haqida gapirib o'tamiz.

Koordinatsiya va muvozanat gandbolda muvaffaqiyat uchun muhimdir. Mashg'ulotlarda turli xil harakatlar orqali ushbu ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor beriladi. Masalan, bir oyog'da turib turli tomonlarga to'p tashlash, bir vaqtning o'zida to'pni boshqarish va yugurish kabi mashqlar.

Maqsad va vazifasi: To'pni boshqarish texnikasini oshirish uchun o'yinchilar to'pni turli tezlikda va holatda boshqarish mashqlarini bajarishadi. Bu texnika nafaqat to'pni olib yurish, balki uni qabul qilish va etkazib berishda ham qo'llaniladi.

Yugurish texnikasini rivojlantirish o'yinchilarning tezligini oshirishda yordam beradi. Tezlik, chidamlilik va chaqqonlikni oshirish uchun turli xil yugurish mashqlari, jumladan intervalli yugurish va zigzag yugurish mashqlari bajariladi.

O'yinchilarga to'pni qanday boshqarish va to'g'ri pas berishni o'rgatish. Bu mashqlarda to'pni tezlikda boshqarish, qo'llar orasida o'tkazish, hamda har xil burchaklarda va masofalarda pas berish amaliyoti o'rgatiladi.

Himoya va hujum texnikasini o'rgatish. O'yinchilarga raqibni to'xtatish, to'pni egallash va hujum qilish uchun eng samarali usullar o'rgatiladi. Himoya chizig'ida to'g'ri joylashish va hujumda to'pni samarali uzatish bu mashg'ulotlarning asosiy qismi hisoblanadi. O'yinchilarning rivojlanishini kuzatish va mashg'ulotlarni

moslashtirish. Har bir o'yinchining individual yondashuvi bo'yicha metodika ishlab chiqiladi va natijalar muntazam ravishda tahlil qilinadi.

Tadqiqot natijasi.

Texnologiyaning rivojlanishi bilan mashg'ulotlarda simulyatsiyalar va interaktiv texnologiyalardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Maxsus dasturlar yordamida o'yinchilar o'z harakatlarini tahlil qilishi va yaxshilashi mumkin. Asosiy ko'nikmalarga urg'u berish: Dastlabki mashg'ulot bosqichida to'p uzatish, dribling, otish va himoyalalanish kabi asosiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishga ustuvor ahamiyat berish kerak. Murabbiylar ushbu usullarni boshqariladigan qismlarga ajratishlari va asta-sekin o'yinchilarni oddiy mashqlardan murakkabroq o'yinga o'xshash stsenariylarga o'tkazishlari kerak. Takroriy mashqlar: takrorlash gandbol texnikasini o'zlashtirishning kalitidir. Muayyan harakatlar va harakatlarni izchil mashq qilish orqali o'yinchilarmushaklar xotirasini yaxshilashlari va bosim ostida o'yin texnikasini bajarish mahoratini oshirishlari mumkin. Kichik qirrali o'yinlar: mashg'ulotlarga kichik qirrali o'yinlarni kiritish o'yinchilarga o'rganilgan usullarni simulyatsiya qilingan o'yin muhitida qo'llash imkoniyatini beradi. Ushbu o'yinlar asosiy ko'nikmalarni mustahkamlash bilan birga qaror qabul qilish, fazoviy xabardorlik va jamoaviy ishlashni rag'batlantiradi. Video tahlili: Video tahlilidan foydalanish murabbiylarga o'yinchilarga vizual fikr-mulohazalarni taqdim etish imkonini beradi, ularga o'z texnikasini yaxshilash va qaror qabul qilish yo'nalishlarini aniqlashga yordam beradi. Professional o'yinchilar va jamoaning o'yinlarini o'yin tasvirlarini tahlil qilish o'yin strategiyasiva taktikasini o'rganish va tushunishni kuchaytirishi mumkin. Jismoniy holatni kuzatish va boshqarish uchun zamonaviy qurilmalardan foydalanish. Puls, nafas olish va boshqa ko'rsatkichlar yordamida o'yinchilarning jismoniy holati nazorat qilinadi va mos mashg'ulotlar belgilanadi.

Xulosa.

Qo'l to'pichilarni tayyorlashda dastlabki texnik tayyorgarlik ularga asosiy ko'nikmalarni egallash va rivojlantirishda yordam beradi. To'g'ri tayyorgarlik dasturi o'yinchilarning nafaqat jismoniy holatini, balki o'yindagi muvaffaqiyatini ham oshiradi. Yuqorida keltirilgan usullar va mashg'ulotlar yordamida yangi o'yinchilarni yuqori darajada tayyorlash mumkin.

Qo'l to'pi bo'yicha samarali boshlang'ich mashg'ulotlar o'yinchilarning o'yin texnikasini o'zlashtirishlari uchun zamin yaratish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Asosiy ko'nikmalarga urg'u berish, takroriy mashqlar, kichik qirrali o'yinlar, video tahlillar va simulyatsiya mashg'ulotlarini amalga oshirish orqali murabbiylar

o'yinchilarga gandbol maydonida ustunlik qilish uchun zarur bo'lgan vositalar va bilimlarni taqdim etishlari mumkin. O'yinchilarning faoliyati davomida ushbu usullarni doimiy ravishda mashq qilish va takomillashtirish ularning malakali va malakali gandbolchi sifatida muvaffaqiyatga erishishiga yordam beradi.

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